
The Relationship between Work-Family Conflict and Work Life Quality of Air Transportation Sector Employees

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Abstract

Aim: It is aimed to evaluate and determine how much work-family conflict affects the quality of work life of air transport sector employees in Istanbul.

Method: The study population of the research consists of those who work in the air transportation sector in Istanbul. The sample of the study, on the other hand, consists of a total of 292 air transport sector employees, 184 women (63%) and 108 men (37%), determined by random sampling. Work Life Quality scale and Work-Family conflict scale were used in the study. Correlation analysis was used to analyze the data. The research was analyzed and interpreted in the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) program, which was obtained using face-to-face questionnaire method.

Results: 63% of the participants in the study are women and 37% are men. The rate of those who are married is 58.9% and the rate of singles is 41.1%. The average age of the sample is 34.4. Correlation analysis was performed between work-family conflict and work life quality, and the relationship between them was found to be significant ($p < 0.05$).

Result: According to the results of the analysis, it was concluded that role conflict of individuals in the fields of work and family is inevitable and that conflict negatively affects individuals' job and life satisfaction. As the job satisfaction increases, the quality of life of the people increases and makes positive contributions to the health, psychological conditions and social environment of the people.

Keywords: Work family conflict, work life quality, air transportation sector employees.

Introduction

As a social being, the individual has many organizational and social roles. The quick change in recent years due to globalization, technological, political, cultural and economic developments has changed the perceptions of individuals regarding their roles. People are born and grow up in a family. They also have a job after a certain period of their lives. Business life is a social environment where individuals generally participate in their employee roles and perform their mental and physical activities (Çelmeçe & Işıklar 2016). Each individual is a member of more than one system or social group in society; Therefore, it has as many roles and responsibilities as the number of groups it is a member of. Conflict becomes inevitable when the energy, time or behavioral demands of the work role intersect with family or personal life roles. The work prevents the responsibilities towards the family, causes work-family conflict, family responsibilities prevent family-work conflict

(Kossek & Lee, 2017).

Role anticipations are an important factor in experiencing work-family conflict. For example, the conflict regarding the job role is caused by the pressure experienced due to excessive job demands and expectations, especially such as excessive workload and lack of time. Most of the studies show that there is a positive and strong relationship between work demands such as working hours, workload, irregular working hours and work-family conflict (Burke, 2002; Alçelik, Deniz, Yeşildal, Mayda, & Şerefi, 2005). Accordingly, excessive daily working hours, being obliged to work at night and weekends, inability of employees to engage in activities related to their families cause them to fail to fulfill their family roles and responsibilities.

The aviation sector is in an unacceptable structure due to the way it works. Airline employees, who interact one-on-one with passengers, are affected by many physical and psychological factors due to their intense work pace and responsibility. Employees who are exposed to

intense working hours and stress can negatively affect family life, on the other hand, problems encountered in their work life (Kossek & Lee, 2017). These problems faced by the person also negatively affect the quality of the product and service offered (Trachtenberg, 2009).

In this organizational structure, the service encounter between customers and employees affects the organizational attitudes and behaviors of both employees and customers. While these moments of encounter and factors originating from the organization affect organizational behavior issues such as job satisfaction, job stress, quality of work life, commitment, leadership, trust, they can also affect customers' perceptions of service quality and satisfaction (Sabli & Marican, 2005). In addition to the intense and uninterrupted pace of working, these organizations, where there are different working systems, sometimes the situations experienced in the business environment are reflected in family life; Sometimes, relationships in the family environment can be reflected in business life and affect the quality of work life of employees (Anderson, Branislav, Vermeylen, Lyly-Yrjanainen, & Zigante, 2009).

Quality of work life is a vital management process that includes the factors that directly affect the efficiency and productivity of the staff at work. According to Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2013), quality of work life is a positive business environment supported by issues such as employee promotion opportunities, job security, and reward system. According to Kılıç and Keklik (2012), evaluation of working conditions, employee satisfaction and dissatisfaction, productivity, social environment at work, management style, relationship between work life and non-work life; In short, it is a concept that includes the strengths and weaknesses of the entire business environment (Kılıç & Keklik, 2012).

As stated in the studies on the factors affecting the work life quality of employees, work life quality, demographic factors, working environment, wages, earnings, working environment and conditions, management and organization of jobs, leaders, technology used at work, industrial relations, participation, employment security, it is affected by objective conditions such as social security and continuing education (Sirgy, Reilly, Wu & Fraty, 2008; Netemeyer, Boles, & Mcmurrin, 1996; Efeoğlu, 2006). Thus, the antecedents of work life quality should be examined. There are many different classifications regarding the factors affecting the quality of work life in the literature. The quality of an individual's work life depends on

many factors both inside and outside work. Work-family conflict is one of these factors.

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between work-family conflict and work life quality of air transport sector employees. In accordance with this purpose;

1. Is there a relationship between work-family conflict and work-life quality of air transport sector employees?
2. Does the work-family conflict of air transport sector employees have an impact on their quality of work? Answers to questions will be sought.

Method

The research was conducted in relational scanning model in order to determine the relationship between work-family conflict and work-life quality of air transport sector employees. The study population of the research consists of those who work in the air transportation sector in Istanbul. The sample of the study, on the other hand, consists of 292 employees, 184 women (63%) and 108 men (37%) determined by random sampling method.

Measurement Tools:

- 1. Socio-demographic Data Form:** It encapsulates a total of 6 questions about socio-demographic and occupational characteristics such as age, gender, marital status, education level, profession, working year.
- 2. Work Family Conflict Scale:** The scale developed by Netemeyer, Boles and McMurrin (1996) including 5 expressions in both dimensions was used to measure the conflict level of the participants in their work-family, family-work lives. According to the reliability analysis, the Cronbach alpha coefficient was reported as 0.88 for work-family conflict and 0.89 for family-work conflict. The scale was adapted to Turkish by Efeoğlu (2006), and Cronbach alpha coefficients were reported as 0.83 for work-family conflict and 0.88 for family-work conflict. Based on this adaptation, the expressions in the scale were rearranged by the researchers in terms of meaning and content by comparing them with the original scale. In this study, the values for the data set for factor analysis were calculated as: KMO = 0.829 and X2 Bartlett test (45) = 2314.613 $p < 0.0001$. According to the results of the factor analysis, two factor structures, both consisting of 5 items, have been preserved and the total explained variance is 63.52%. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients were calculated as 0.884

for work-family conflict and 0.810 for family-work conflict.

3. Work Life Quality Scale: The Quality of Work Life Scale was developed in 2001 by Sirgy, Efraty, Siegel and Lee. The scale consists of 16 items related to the satisfaction of 16 needs. All of the items that make up the scale aim to measure the quality of work life in the workplace. The first three items (1., 2., 3.) of the scale are aimed at measuring the satisfaction of health and safety needs. Items 4, 5 and 6 are aimed at measuring the satisfaction of family and economic needs. Articles 7 and 8 are aimed at measuring the satisfaction of social needs. Articles 9 and 10 are aimed at measuring the satisfaction level of the need for respect. Items 11 and 12 are intended to measure to what extent the need for self-actualization is satisfied. Articles 13 and 14 are intended to measure to what extent the need for information is satisfied. 15 and 16 questions are about the satisfaction level of aesthetic needs. In order to test the construct validity of the original scale, a confirmatory factor analysis was performed by Sirgy, Efraty, Siegel, and Lee (2001), and it was revealed that 16 items came from seven factors and these seven factors came from a single factor. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of the Work Quality of Life Scale was calculated as 0.78.

Findings

In the study; 63% of the participants are female and 37% are male. The rate of those who are married is 58.9% and the rate of singles is 41.1%. The average age of the sample is 34.4. Average values and standard deviations of research variables are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean Values and Standard Deviation of Variables

	\bar{X}	S
Work Family Conflict	3.98	1.51
Family Work Conflict	3.83	1.50
Work Life Quality	2.96	1.92

Table 1 indicates values for dependent and independent variables used according to descriptive statistics obtained from 292 employees. When Table 1 is analyzed, it is seen that the scores of conflict levels from work to family are higher than scores for conflict from family to work. The scores on the quality of work life of air transport

sector employees are at medium level. Pearson correlation analysis was applied to test the relationship between work-family conflict levels and sub-dimensions of work-to-family conflict and family-to-work conflict levels of employees and their work life quality. The results of the correlation test are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation values of the relationship between work-family conflict / family-work conflict and work-life quality of air transport sector employees.

Variables	1	2	3
1. Work Family Conflict	-		
2. Family Work Conflict	.428**	-	
3. Work Life Quality	.437**	.456**	-

** p<0.01

When Table 2 is examined, there is a moderate positive relationship between work-family conflict sub-dimension of the Work-Family Conflict Scale and family-work conflict sub-dimension $r = .428$ ($p < .01$), while between work-family conflict sub-dimension and work-life quality $r = -.437$ ($p < .01$), a moderately negative correlation was found between family-work conflict sub-dimension and work life quality, $r = -.456$ ($p < .01$). As work-family conflict increases, so does family-work conflicts of employees. In addition, as work-family conflict and family-work conflict increase, the quality of work life of employees decreases.

The results of regression analysis related to the effect of work-family conflicts of employees on their work life quality are presented in Table 3. Regression analyzes were conducted to reveal direct relationships between variables, in other words, the explanatory power of independent variables on dependent variables. In the regression analyzes, Work Life Quality was considered as the dependent variable and the effects on the dependent variable were examined by taking Work-Family Conflict as an independent variable.

As can be seen in Table 3, it is seen that work-family conflict has a negative and significant effect on the quality of work life ($\beta = -0.40$; $p \leq 0.01$). Work-family conflict explains the quality of work life by 14% ($R^2 = .17$). According to these results, the level of work-family conflict of air transport sector employees negatively affects their work life quality.

Table 3. Regression values of the effect of work-family conflict on work-life quality of air transport sector employees

	Work Life Quality			
	β	T	F	p
Work Family Conflict	-0,400	-4,525	20,476	0,000
	R2 = 0,170			

*p<0,01

Discussion

Conflict between work and family life arises because of the multiple roles individuals have to play and the increased responsibilities that result from these multiple roles played. On the one hand, individuals who fulfill / try to fulfill their responsibilities related to the employee role in business life; On the other hand, motherhood / fatherhood, accompaniment, etc. in family life, and trying to fulfill their responsibilities regarding their roles. In this case, it is inevitable for individuals to experience conflicts. It is seen that researches on work-family conflict are mainly conducted in various fields in North America and Western European countries (Anderson, Branislav, Vermeylen, Lyly-Yrjanainen, & Zigante, 2009; Sirgy, Efraty, Siegel, & Lee, 2001; Trachtenberg, 2009). Our research was conducted on air transport sector workers with heavy workloads, irregular work schedules and difficult working hours.

In the study, it was found that air transport sector employees experienced moderate work-family conflict, their average work-family conflict was higher than their family-work conflict averages, and they had a moderate work-life quality. This finding is supported by some of the studies in the literature (Cinamon, & Rich, 2005; Gareis, Barnett, Ertel, & Berkman, 2009). In the study of Anafarta (2011), looking at the relationship between work-family conflict and job satisfaction on airline employees, it was observed that airline employees experienced work-family conflict more than family-work conflict. In the study conducted by Mashe et al. on 727 doctors in Germany in 2015, the work-family conflict rates of doctors were found to be higher than the family-work conflict rates. In studies by Powell, Francesco, and Ling (2009), investigating the role of social support in work-family conflict on women working in the informatics sector, the rates of work-family conflict were found to be high. These findings support our research.

A moderately negative relationship was found between work-family conflicts and work-life quality of air transport sector employees participating in the study. In a study conducted by Kiraç, Demir and Kahveci (2018) with 225 healthcare workers in Konya, it was found that work-family conflict

negatively affected the quality of work life. Nkulenu (2015), study on the job satisfaction and career satisfaction of the work-family conflict on cabin crew found a moderate and negative relationship between job-family conflict and job satisfaction. Md-Sidin, Sambasivan, and Ismail (2010), found strong negative relationships between work-family conflict and work-life quality in their research on 335 employees. Nkulenu, (2015), found that work-family conflict negatively affected the quality of work life in their study, where they examined the relationship between work-family conflict and work-life quality. These findings support our research.

Results

The most fundamental indispensables of individuals are their jobs and families. If individuals pay too much attention to their jobs, their families will suffer, and if they care too much about their families, they may disrupt their work. Therefore, allocating more shares to one of the two elements mentioned may negatively affect both concepts. In this direction, the relationship between work-family conflicts and work life quality has been tried to be examined. At the same time, it was tried to determine in which life area the employees had the most conflicts between work and family and family to work. In addition, work-family and family business conflicts; it has also been examined whether it has an impact on the quality of work life. As a result of the research; there was a significant negative correlation between work-to-family conflicts and family-to-work conflicts and work life quality. A statistically significant difference was found between work-to-family conflicts and family-to-work conflicts. Accordingly, it was ended up that conflicts reflected from work to family were higher.

There is a need for factors that will reduce work-family conflict of air transport sector employees and increase the quality of work life. Managers should apply an 'open door policy' to their subordinates in order to increase the quality of work life and minimize work-family life conflict, and a participatory working environment where employees can be comfortable should be provided. Employees should comfortably share their ideas with their managers and feel valued in their

business. Knowing that employees in complex organizations with too many employees are valuable for that institution, such as the air transport sector, will increase satisfaction and be happier in both business and family life. At the same time, it is thought that the organizational and social support to be provided to the employee will increase the quality of work life and reduce work-family life conflict.

Once again, in the researches, it was determined that working hours are determinant in work-family conflict. Accordingly, as the working hours decrease, the time pressure on the employee decreases and it becomes easier for them to balance their work and family life. In the opposite case; that is, when working hours increase; the time pressure on the employee increases, causing work-family conflict. It is considered that the regulation of working hours of air transport sector employees will lead to a decrease in work-family conflicts and an increase in the quality of work life.

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